

Shared Parcels Lockers for Customer Convenience

Jaco Voorspuij - FixLog Consulting

October 2025

Sofoklis Dais, Katerina Batzou, Georgia Ayfantopoulou - Centre for Research and Technology Hellas

Jorge Melero Corell - Terminal Industry Committee 4.0

Urban last-mile networks are increasingly fragmented as multiple carriers deploy proprietary parcel-locker stations that can locate very near one another or, conversely, be spaced far apart where curb and sidewalk space is constrained. In a metropolitan case study of 176 Amazon lockers in Portland, 69.3% were sited at convenience stores and "mostly installed on sidewalks and public access areas", underscoring competition for scarce urban space; despite this, nearly 85% of households were still within 1.5 miles of a locker, highlighting how accessibility varies by neighbourhood (Schaefer & Figliozzi, 2021).

Consumer choice studies consistently show a baseline preference for home delivery, with stated-preference evidence from Rome reporting 81.5% of e-purchasers preferring home delivery over lockers or service points, and distance to the locker emerging as a key deterrent (Iannaccone et al., 2021). Likewise, discrete-choice experiments find access distance and reliability dominate preferences; when lockers are farther away, consumers revert to home delivery, but when costs for home delivery rise and locker networks densify (reducing travel distance), the modeled share of home delivery can drop dramatically (e.g., from 71% to 7% in Dutch scenarios) (Molin et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024).

These preference patterns have direct traffic implications. Empirical and modeling work indicates that delivering to lockers (with recipients consolidating pickups) can markedly reduce delivery activity and emissions relative to home delivery, with synthesis studies reporting 18.7–51.2% CO₂ reductions for locker-based scenarios depending on user travel to the locker and urban form, and some models finding locker deliveries can produce as little as ~5% of home-delivery emissions under favorable conditions (Schnieder et al., 2021). Field evidence further shows parcel lockers reduce time inside buildings for couriers (statistically significant) and slightly reduce curb dwell time (not statistically significant), both consistent with higher stop productivity and fewer vehicle-minutes in congested areas (Ranjbari et al., 2023).

Taken together, the literature suggests that where locker siting is constrained by limited urban space (pushing stations farther from recipients) consumers shift toward home delivery; if this trend persists without countervailing policies (e.g., expanding common-carrier lockers or densifying networks), vehicle activity in already congested urban areas can be expected to rise (Janinhoff et al., 2024; Kahr et al., 2022).

Using shared parcel stations, placed in locations that Consumers frequent anyway, may reverse the undesirable trend indicated in the literature.

The ambition of the FOR-FREIGHT project is to provide a concept idea or the deployment of a large network of shared parcel stations across Metro stations, enabling consumers to collect their parcels conveniently as part of their daily routine. This concept has already been partially tested in Madrid through collaboration between Metro de Madrid and a logistics service provider (LSP).

Once implemented, the transportation of parcels to these parcel stations can be consolidated, regardless of the seller or the logistics service provider initially selected – often located far from the destination city.

Providing consumers with access to a large number of parcel stations throughout the Metro network offers a wide range of benefits:

- Consumers can always collect their parcels from the same convenient locker station, regardless of the original sender or the urban edge warehouse.
- More consumers are likely to choose parcel-station delivery for their online purchases.
- Fewer delivery vehicles will be required for home deliveries, reducing urban traffic.
- This leads to lower congestion and pollution from all vehicles in the city.

- Quality of life improves for urban residents.
- The total logistics cost of last-mile delivery is reduced.

Together, these advantages create a strong business case for all stakeholders involved in urban parcel logistics to participate in developing and deploying this approach.

The concept is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1: Scheme of the transportation methods

A seller sends parcels containing purchased items in bulk to the destination country (for example, via a port), as shown in the top row. These parcels are then transported to a warehouse or depot near the destination city, in this example, Madrid, as shown in the middle row. Since there may be many sellers sending parcels, multiple warehouses may exist around the city. From these warehouses, parcels must then be transported to the parcel stations located within the Metro network, as illustrated in the bottom row.

The Metro operator can act as a central and neutral party responsible for transporting parcels from the Metro depots through the Metro network to the parcel stations. The Metro operator may also operate the parcel stations or rely on partners to do so.

To enable this process, the flow of parcels must be supported by standardized information flows, including:

- A common parcel identifier used from the sender all the way to the parcel station.
- Common identifiers for all locations involved in the flow, such as parcel stations, city-edge warehouses, Metro depots, and Metro stations.
- Common identifiers for handling equipment shared between city-edge warehouses and the Metro operator during parcel transport and equipment returns.

Each seller assigns a globally unique identifier (e.g., GS1 SSCC ¹) for every parcel created. The seller links all necessary delivery information to this identifier and shares it with their LSP.

The city-edge warehouse LSP receives the parcels based on their SSCC codes and associated information, including the data related to the consumer who ordered the items. The LSP then communicates the relevant delivery information (including the SSCC) to the Metro operator, who plans the delivery of parcels to the appropriate parcel stations within the Metro network. The set of parcel stations used will evolve over time, as consumers register their preferred collection stations with the Metro operator, preferences can change as needed.

The Metro operator informs the warehouse LSP which parcels should be transported to the Metro depot. At the depot, parcels are loaded onto Metro trains for delivery to the designated parcel stations. Typically, the warehouse LSP groups parcels by parcel station into shared transport equipment and links each SSCC to its corresponding equipment ID. The handover at the Metro depot and the subsequent transport through the Metro network are then managed based on these equipment IDs. At the parcel stations, the SSCC is used to ensure each parcel is placed into the correct locker. The consumer is then notified that the parcel is available for collection and receives a code to open the locker. Finally, the empty transport equipment is returned from the parcel stations to the originating warehouse for reuse.

The figure below illustrates how the information linked to the parcel may be used by all parties involved.

Figure 2: Information usage by all parties.

Each parcel would have a label based on global standards affixed at the seller’s despatch location, as shown in the centre of the figure. This label contains the common parcel ID in both a linear and a 2D barcode. Each stakeholder in the logistics chain can use this ID to access the related information. In many cases, this information will be exchanged before the parcels reach the logistics service provider (LSP). However, the 2D barcode also includes a URL pointing to an online resource where the latest parcel information can be accessed. For example, updates or

¹SSCC = Serial Shipping Container Code compliant with ISO/IEC 15459-1

delivery changes requested by the consumer. Both the linear and 2D barcodes comply with international standards (e.g., ISO, W3C and GS1) that have been proven to operate reliably at scale for decades, ensuring safe and interoperable use in any environment.

The above concept represents a highly consumer-centric approach. Consumers can indicate their preferred parcel station for collection. They only need to interact with the Metro operator, there is no need to inform multiple online sellers.

Additionally, this approach will help reduce the negative impacts on urban living conditions and the environment associated with the ever-increasing number of parcels ordered by consumers in cities. The significantly improved convenience it offers may also help prevent consumers from choosing home delivery more frequently (as mentioned in the literature above).

Importantly, this solution can be implemented immediately using existing, well-established standards that are easily integrated into current IT and operational environments. There is no technical barrier, only the need for collective willingness among stakeholders to adopt this consumer-centric approach for the benefit of all parties involved.

References

- Chen, J., Li, R., Ma, J., & An, Q. (2024). Stationary versus mobile parcel lockers: Which self-service technology moves the consumers in the last mile of urban areas? *Travel Behaviour and Society*, 35, 100742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2024.100742>
- Iannaccone, G., Marcucci, E., & Gatta, V. (2021). What young e-consumers want? Forecasting parcel lockers choice in Rome. *Logistics*, 5(3), 57. <https://doi.org/10.3390/logistics5030057>
- Janinhoff, L., Klein, R., Sailer, D., & Schoppa, J. M. (2024). Out-of-home delivery in last-mile logistics: A review. *Computers & Operations Research*, 168, 106686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cor.2024.106686>
- Jiang, L., Chang, H., Zhao, S., Dong, J., & Lu, W. (2019). A travelling salesman problem with carbon emission reduction in the last mile delivery. *IEEe Access*, 7, 61620-61627. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2915634>
- Kahr M. (2022). Determining locations and layouts for parcel lockers to support supply chain viability at the last mile. *Omega*, 113, 102721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2022.102721>
- Molin, E., Kosicki, M., & Van Duin, R. (2022). Consumer preferences for parcel delivery methods: The potential of parcel locker use in the Netherlands. *European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research*, 22(2), 183-200. <https://doi.org/10.18757/ejtir.2022.22.2.6427>
- Ranjbari, A., Diehl, C., Dalla Chiara, G., & Goodchild, A. (2023). Do parcel lockers reduce delivery times? Evidence from the field. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 172, 103070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2023.103070>
- Schaefer, J. S., & Figliozzi, M. A. (2021). Spatial accessibility and equity analysis of Amazon parcel lockers facilities. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 97, 103212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2021.103212>
- Schnieder, M., Hinde, C., & West, A. (2021). Sensitivity Analysis of Emission Models of Parcel Lockers vs. Home Delivery Based on HBEFA. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(12), 6325. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18126325>